

LIGHTWEIGHT DESIGN OF COMPOSITE BODY FOR ELECTRIC MICROBUS

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Keywords: Composite plates, Modal analysis, Identification, Properties, Finite elements

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to propose a preliminary design methodology for electric bus structures by implementing the finite-element method via HyperWorks 2017. The bus structure is designed based on various criteria such as the strength of the bus structure under various driving conditions, bending and torsion stiffness requirements and the rollover test according to UN ECE R66. The objective function is to minimize the mass and the cost of the material for the microbus body having varied lamina thickness and stacking sequence. The weight, global and local stiffnesses of all above parts of the sandwich body are analyzed in order to obtain the best capability values under various conditions. The weight of the base model with uniform thickness and lay-up in all parts is approximately 2,681 kilograms and costs 29,708 USD. This model is deliberately chosen based on the overall maximum displacement of 2 mm under the bending mode. The mass-optimized model yields the structural weight of 1,677 kilograms yet having an identical constraint of the vertical displacement as the base model and costs 23,907 USD. The cost-optimized model, on the other hand, weighs 1,972 kilograms but the cost is greatly reduced to 16,488 USD.

1 INTRODUCTION

Many countries around the world have addressed the problem related to air pollution and, in recent year, there has been many platforms at international level to discuss how to tackle air pollution and environmental issues. One of many solutions to effectively reduces severity of the environmental problems arising from road transport is to promote the use of electric vehicles (EVs), especially in mega-cities. Another suggestion, if combined with above solution may yield significantly higher impact, is to encourage people to use more public transport and avoid travelling alone using personal car. Some countries have also announced plan to reduce or ban diesel cars, which is the source of air pollution and particulate matter emissions. Therefore, the development and advancement of EV technologies can lead to cleaner future in transportation [1].

In the design of any electric vehicle structure, the main factors that should be considered are the strength, weight and usable space. These factors are inter-related and also affects the energy efficiency and driving range, as well as the performance, significantly. Lightweight concept has been adopted and emphasised in many automotive companies and involves many possible approaches, such as redesign of structure and parts, decrease material volume and change material type. Fiber reinforced composites, therefore, received more attention as it exhibits higher strength, stiffness to weight ratios compared to conventional metal counterparts. Moreover, manufacturing flexibility is another advantage of the composites which leads to great benefits when optimization process is combined. Velea, et al. [2] developed a compact electric vehicle body where single-objective and multi-objective optimization studies are defined as the optimum thickness and distribution for composite layers. Testoni, [3] designed an urban electric bus using composite sandwich structure. The electric bus monocoque body is developed. The bus body was subjected to normal driving loads and roll-over

crash complying with UN ECE R66. The unidirectional carbon fibre is used to reduce strain at pillar and window components.

This paper, therefore, aims to propose a lightweight design methodology for an intercity microbus monocoque body using lay-up optimization techniques. The materials considered are fibre-reinforced composites, i.e. glass and carbon fibre woven fabrics/epoxy. Sandwich structures are utilized in all main load carrying body parts with composite face sheets and flame-retardant foam core. The structural simulation is performed using the finite-element method via HyperWorks 2017 with optimization module Altair OptiStruct™. To achieve independent analysis and optimization in each body part, the bus body is divided into various sections. Three cases of load conditions – static bending mode, static torsion mode and driving mode, are investigated.

2 GENERAL SPECIFICATIONS

2.1 General model information

The electric microbus in this study is designed for intercity transport. This microbus features a monocoque structure which can accommodate 24 passengers. The dimensions of the bus are 2.4 meters wide, 7.8 meters long, and 3.2 meters high. The upper and lower passenger floors, the lower part, are connected to the shaft and drive system. There is a service door on the left side of the bus and emergency door on the right side. The battery is set between the front and rear axles under the cabin floor. To identify the battery capacity required for the electric microbus, the current relationship between power consumption and gross vehicle weight (GVW) of other electric buses is used [4-9]. The electric microbus in this study is designed for a driving range of 300 km per charge. The energy consumption is estimated to be approximately 0.83 kWh/km as shown in Figure 1. The estimated weight is 8,575 kilograms as shown in Table 1 along with other details of the base model. The battery capacity is determined to be 320 kWh. However, the battery capacity of 256 kWh can power the microbus for 308 kilometres. This is higher than 300 km and with a power density of a lithium-ion battery of 250 Wh/kg, the battery weight is estimated to be 1,280 kilograms.

Components	Weight (kg)
Front axle	482
Rear axle (in-wheel motors)	950
12 double seats and driver seat	407
Tire 265/70 R 19.5	540
24 Passengers + driver	1515
Air conditioning	270
Battery pack	1280
Body structure	2681
2 Door	180
Windows	230
Total	8535

Table 1: Mass breakdown of the base model

Figure 1: Relationship between energy consumption and gross vehicle weight of electric buses

2.2 Material properties

Most parts of the monocoque structure of the microbus are designed to be manufactured using the sandwich structure consisting of woven fabrics composite and foam core. The type of foam core is DIVINYCELL HP [10] which has been developed to exhibit impressive mechanical performance and low weight. Three types of woven fabric are used, which are woven E-glass fabric with the density of 400 g/m² (G400), woven E-glass fabric with the density of 600 g/m² (G600) and woven carbon fabric with the density of 200 g/m² (C200) and their mechanical properties are shown in Table 2. All of the material properties are obtained from testing according to relevant ASTM standards; ASTM D3039 for tensile properties, ASTM D3410 for compressive properties and ASTM D3518 for in-plane shear properties.

Material properties	G400	G600	C200	HP100
Longitudinal modulus, E_1 (MPa)	18,036	16,281	78,493	105
Transverse modulus, E_2 (MPa)	18,036	16,281	78,493	
In-plane shear modulus, G_{12} (MPa)	2,219	2,942	2,122	28
Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.053	0.04	0.052	0.4
Longitudinal tensile strength, F_{1t} (MPa)	206.6	309	411.4	2.5
Longitudinal compressive strength, F_{1c} (MPa)	97.8	195	370.6	1.65
Transverse tensile strength, F_{2t} (MPa)	206.6	309	411.4	
Transverse compressive strength, F_{2c} (MPa)	97.8	195	370.6	
In-plane shear strength, S_{12} (MPa)	27.45	27.9	22.4	35
Density (kg/m ³)	1,588	1,717	1,336	100
Material cost per kilograms (USD)	5.5	3.8	111	18.8

Table 2: Material properties of glass and carbon fiber prepregs and foam core.

2.3 Design Criteria

In order to design the bus structure to meet mass or cost requirements, three factors need to be considered. These are 1) structural stiffness under normal operating conditions, 2) driving conditions which relate to static and dynamic loads, and 3) safety requirement, especially the roll over case. From the above factors, six design and optimization constraints can be formulated as follows

- 1) Bending stiffness (K_b) is an ability to handle the bending force on the body due to weight and load and it can be determined from the total weight of the structure and the deflection under bending load. The body structure can be assumed as a simply supported beam. The Bending stiffness is calculated as a ratio of the gross vehicle weight (W) and the maximum deformation of the structure (d_{max}) under the bending case as presented in Equation (1). The criterion for bending stiffness requirement is that the bending stiffness must be over 36,000 N/mm. This value is estimated from the bus dimensions and the resonance frequency [11].

$$K_b = \frac{W}{d_{max}} \quad (1)$$

- 2) Torsional stiffness (K_t) is the ability to handle the torque applied to the vehicle structure due to inadequate road conditions, such as diaphragm or road pits. To determine the torsional stiffness, the bus is loaded on the front wheels in opposite direction while the rear wheels are fixed to twist the structure. The twisting angle θ measured at the front axle is used to calculate the torsional stiffness using Equation (2)

$$K_t = \frac{Ft}{\theta} \quad (2)$$

where t is the length of the front axle and F is the reaction force at front wheel. The torsional stiffness requirement is more than 40,000 Nm/deg [12].

- 3) Natural frequency of the body structure is taken into account for deflections that may occur due to vibrations caused by road condition. The natural frequency of the first mode should be higher than 5 Hz [13].
- 4) Longitudinal loading is the load on the structure due to acceleration of 0.75 g in the longitudinal direction.
- 5) Lateral loading is the load on the lateral side of the bus structure during cornering. The acceleration of 0.75g is used.
- 6) Quasi- static loading test [14] concerns the impact resistance and strength of superstructure of passenger vehicles under virtual rollover test. A rigid beam, which is longer than the superstructure used to simulate the ground in a rollover test, pushes the roof of the superstructure. The direction of the applied load (shown in Figure 2) is related to the longitudinal vertical centre plane of the vehicle and its inclination shall be determined as follows

$$\alpha = 90^{\circ} - \arcsin\left(\frac{800}{H_c}\right) \quad (3)$$

where:

α = Longitudinal vertical centre plane of the vehicle and its inclination

H_c = The superstructure height (mm) of the vehicle measured from the horizontal plane on which it is standing.

Figure 2: Application of load to the body section

From the load-deformation curve, the actual energy absorbed can be expressed as the area below the curve. Evaluation of test result is considered the minimum energy (E_T) required to be absorbed by the superstructure determined as follows

$$E_T = 0.75 M g \Delta h \quad (4)$$

where

M = The kerb mass of the vehicle (kg)

g = The gravitational constant (m/s^2)

Δh = The vertical movement of the vehicle centre of gravity during a rollover test, shown in Figure 3 (m)

Figure 3: Determination of the vertical movement of the vehicle centre of gravity

2.4 Analysis of the base model

The bus structure is partitioned into 9 components as shown in Figure 4. The sandwich structure of the base model is symmetric and consists of 8-mm faces and 40-mm foam core as shown in Table 3. The stacking sequence of the faces includes G400/epoxy 0/90 direction; G400/epoxy 45/-45 direction; G600/epoxy 0/90 direction; and G600/epoxy 45/-45 direction. Except floor, battery, and sub floor components, all components are orderly arranged by the above sequences from outer to inner. The roof component has the same sequential as all of above components but no foam core. The battery tray component is C200 face instead of G400 face. Sub floor component has asymmetric structure where its face is sequenced by C200/epoxy 0/90 direction; and C200/epoxy 45/-45 direction. Fiber orientation of the side of bus structure is aligned with x-axis whereas of front and back of bus structure is aligned with y-axis. Stress distributions, damages, and displacement of the bus structure are advertent parameter. The meshes of body structure are 3-node and 4-node shell element formulation with the size of 30-mm.

Figure 4: Components on the electric bus body

Analysis result of the base model under six load cases is shown in Figure 5. Figure 5 (a) shows the deformation of the microbus structure under bending load, maximum deformation of 2.42 mm occurs at the battery compartment. Bending stiffness (K_b), calculated from maximum deformation expressed by Equation (1), is 34,600 N/mm which is less than the requirement of 36,000 N/mm. For the torsional case shown in Figure 5 (b), the front wheels of the model carry the couple force of 217 kN. As a result, the torsional stiffness (K_t) is 106,000 Nm/degree which exceeds the torsional stiffness criterion. The normal driving case shown in Figure 6 (a) displaying stress distribution in the X-axis resulted from longitudinal loading case. High stresses can be noticed at the areas near the corner of window area and alongside the roof. Figure 6 (b) shows the results from the lateral loading case. The stress distribution in the Y axis presents at the upper and lower sections of the side pillars. The base modes of bending and torsion are determined from modal analysis and they are 14.3 and 17.9 Hz, respectively. For quasi-static loading test, the rigid plane is pressed at angle of 15-degree with respect to Z-axis as shown in Figure 7. The deformation is 139 mm at 40,000 joules which passes the requirement.

Figure 5: Deformation under bending and torsion cases (mm)

Figure 6: (a) Stress distribution (σ_{11}) under longitudinal loading and (b) Stress distribution (σ_{22}) under lateral loading (MPa)

According to the considerations of the base model, the bus structure can be further developed in the next process. Battery region carries heavy battery and is a critical area. Floor needs to withstand the weight of all passengers and driver, and sub floor is supported by beam under the cabin. Pillars are the main component to resist the impact of the rollover test. Bottom component is the base structure supporting the driving system and all components. Ceiling plane and the vent is upper cabin holding the air conditioning system. Beam component is the connector between pillars. Roof component is a thin plane made of woven fabric without core foam.

Figure 7: Result of quasi-static loading test

3 OPTIMIZATION PROCESS

In optimization process, the ply thickness of the sandwich structure is an important parameter that governs the function of the components and compliance with the constraints. Strength and stiffness are main requirements for designing the body structure. However, increasing the strength and stiffness of the structure also increase the mass of the structure. Therefore, the optimization process is the effective way to compromise between light and stiff.

3.1 Constraints and objective functions

For the initial analysis, the bus structure comprises of 9 components which are roof, ceiling plane, air vent, pillar, beam, bottom, battery tray, floor and sub floor as shown in Figure 4. To optimize the base model, the thicknesses of face and core of each component are modified, and the result structure must pass all criteria defined in Section 2.3. The upper bound of responses for torsion case is 2.3 mm which can be deduced from bending stiffness requirement as expressed in Equation (5).

$$\omega_n = \frac{22.4}{\sqrt{48}} \left(\frac{l}{L} \right)^{1.5} \sqrt{\frac{K}{M}} \quad (5)$$

where ω = Bending resonant frequency (22-25 Hz)
 M = Total mass (kg)
 L = Overall length (mm)
 K = Required bending stiffness of the body (kg/mm)
 l = Wheelbase (mm)

For torsional stiffness, a couple force of 121 kN is applied on both front wheels. As a result, the range of responses is between -100 to 100 mm. The constraint of natural frequency is determined to be lower than 5 Hz based on the surface profile of the road. Another constraint of design variables involves the ply thickness which must not exceed 4 mm for the face and 50 mm for the core. The objective functions defined for this study are minimizing material cost and minimizing structural mass.

3.2 Size optimization results

In the optimization process, there are 2 models involve in the analysis focusing on mass and cost minimization, which in this study referred to as “mass-optimized” and “cost-optimized” models. Both models are subjected to similar constraints, limit bound and objectives.

In this process, most of laminate thicknesses are decreased since defining minimize mass objective. The results of optimization for minimum mass objective are shown in Table 3. Each block represents ply thickness of 0.4 mm for face and 10 mm for core. The sub floor laminate thickness is raised because the floor component is less thick than original. The weight of the bottom component is decreased by 182 kg or 6.7% compared with structure weight of the base model. For battery tray, the thickness of C200 plies and foam core are increased but thickness G600 plies are decreased. The weight of the battery component is 214 kg increasing from the base model of 178 kg. The most changed component is the roof component which its thickness varies from 16 mm to 4.8 mm. The K_b and K_t obtained are 36,706 N/mm and 124,000 Nm/deg, respectively, which pass the stiffness requirements. Natural frequency of the mass bus model is 16.4 Hz in bending mode and 18.3 Hz in torsion mode. The structural mass of the design is 1,667 kg which is 62% less than the base model and the raw materials cost using the mass-optimized model is 23,907 USD.

The proposed materials for cost-optimized model are also shown in Table 3. The thickness of C200 of battery component is decreased by 0.8 mm but the G200 layer thickness is increased by 4 mm due to the upper bound limit. The core thickness of vent component is decreased to 10 mm due to the lower bound limit. For pillar and beam components, the core thickness is halved. The face thickness of other components seems to reduce from the base model. The bending and torsional stiffnesses of this bus structure are 37,268 N/mm and 114,814 N.mm/deg, respectively. The result of frequency, the first mode of bending and torsion is 14.5 Hz and 18.6 Hz, respectively. The raw material cost of this model is 16,488 USD.

Mass-optimized and cost-optimized model are selected to perform rollover simulation analysis by means of the rigid plane sheet push on the roof of body structure. The contact angle is 15-degree from Z-axis, moving in a stable distance up to 500 mm. The deformation of the mass-optimized model is 138 mm at 33,672 joules which this deformation does not intrude the residual space as shown in Figure 8. The deformation of the cost-optimized model is 161 mm at 35,376 joules and the residual

space structure is noninvasive. The minimum absorbed energy is found from Equation (4), inferring that the optimized model passes the UNECE regulation 66. For the longitudinal load, stress distribution of two optimized model is higher than the base model. Stress distribution of mass-optimized model of longitudinal loading is increased from base model, but the stress distribution of cost-optimized model is decreased.

To sum up, the design of the monocoque structure of the microbus is focused on two objectives, which are to minimize mass and minimize cost of material. Those results are shown in Table 4. The carbon woven faces play important role in supporting battery and passengers in the mass-optimized model. In the cost-optimized model, the glass woven faces are compensated by carbon woven face in various components as this face is low-cost density.

Figure 8: Relationship between load and deformation of quasi-static loading test

	BASE MODEL									MASS MODEL									COST MODEL								
Ply thickness																											
Component	ceiling	pillar	battery	bottom	beam	floor	vent	roof	sub-floor	ceiling	pillar	battery	bottom	beam	floor	vent	roof	sub-floor	ceiling	pillar	battery	bottom	beam	floor	vent	roof	sub-floor
Thickness (mm)	56	56	56	56	56	56	56	16	48	65	64	63	61	56	55	54	4.8	23	63	35	69	64	34	47	18	5.6	12
Cost (1,000 USD)	1.36	1.46	10.0	5.40	0.42	6.24	1.50	2.39	0.94	1.48	1.54	10.8	5.07	0.33	2.22	1.00	0.75	0.65	1.24	1.04	5.07	5.20	0.29	1.91	0.56	0.82	0.37
Mass (kg)	198	213	213	787	62	459	219	521	11	195	200	179	604	27	193	84	154	31	171	192	277	748	53	242	103	184	12

Table 3: Ply thickness of base model, mass-optimized model and cost-optimized model

	Stiffness		Frequency		Raw material cost (USD)	Total mass (kg)
	Bending (N/mm)	Torsion (mm/degree)	Bending (Hz)	Torsion (Hz)		
Base model	34,600	106,000	14.3	17.9	29,708	2,682
Mass model	36,706	124,000	16.4	18.3	23,907	1,667
Cost model	37,268	114,814	14.5	18.6	16,488	1,972

Table 4: Comparison between cost and mass of base model, mass-optimized model and cost-optimized model.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the design and optimization of sandwich structure consisting of glass and carbon fiber/epoxy face and foam core for electric microbus. The sandwich structure is designed based on six constraints which are bending stiffness, torsion stiffness, natural frequency, two normal driving loading criteria, and rollover test. Nine components of bus structure are optimized based on minimizing mass and cost. The optimized structure shows improved performance and is lighter or cheaper. Two optimized models, mass-optimized and cost-optimized, are compared with the base model. However, for these models, the structural deformation under rollover criteria is not considered in the optimization process and would be further developed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support provided by the Thailand Research Fund (TRF), contract no. RDG6050041.

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